

Testing Quetelet's Biological Explanation for the Age Crime Curve

Thomas K. Arnold

University of Cincinnati

arnoldtk@mail.uc.edu

320-252-4993

The age crime curve provides the probability distribution of crime by age. Population level age crime curves generally indicate that criminal activity is low in early childhood, rises rapidly to a peak in late adolescence, and then declines with age until few people commit crimes in old age. There have been few successful attempts to fit a mathematical model to the age crime curve. Quetelet (1831/1984) had proposed that changes in strength, passion, and reason over the life course provided a biological explanation for the age crime curve. This paper provides a test of Quetelet's hypotheses that is limited to an examination of how changes in strength and brain capacity match changes in arrest rates over the life course. The results of these analyses suggest that the age crime curve can be considered to be a cumulative probability distribution with three sections, 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98. A mathematical model that assumes that criminal propensity is normally distributed and posits that Z-scores for the age crime curve are a combination of the strength and brain capacity trajectories over the life course appears to provide an excellent fit to the age crime curve data. The implications of these findings will be discussed.

CONCERNING THE INFLUENCE OF AGE ON THE PROPENSITY FOR CRIME

Among all the causes which have an influence for developing or halting the propensity for crime, the most vigorous is, without contradiction, age. It is, in fact, with age that man's physical strength and passions develop and that their energy afterwards diminishes. It is also with age that reason develops which still continues to grow when strength and passions have already exceeded their maximum intensity. In considering only these three elements, strength, passion, and reason in man, it could be said almost a priori what must be the degrees of the propensity for crime at different ages. This propensity must be practically nil at both extremes of life since, on the one hand, strength and passions, those two powerful instruments of crime, have scarcely been born, and when, on the other hand, their energy (pretty nearly extinguished) is found weakened by the influence of reason. The propensity for crime, on the contrary, must be at its maximum at the age where the strength and passions have attained their maximum, and where reason has not acquired sufficient command to dominate their combined influence. In considering, then, only physical causes, the propensity for crime at different ages would depend especially on the three qualities of which we have just spoken, and would be determined by them if they were sufficiently understood.

Adolphe Quetelet (1831/1984; pp. 54-55)

Testing Quetelet's Biological Explanation for the Age Crime Curve

Adolphe Quetelet (1831/1984) analyzed arrest rates in France in the early 1800s for people of various ages and found that there was a curious pattern. Arrest rates were very low for children and then grew to a peak in late adolescence and young adulthood. The rates of arrest by age then started falling almost as rapidly as they had climbed, declining over the life course until few people were arrested for committing crimes in old age. Quetelet (pp. 54-55) proposed a biological explanation for the age distribution of crime that involved strength, passion and reason. Strength and passion were posited to be low in the very young and the very old, and high in adolescence when reason had not yet reached its peak. Crime was proposed to follow the same increasing and decreasing pattern as strength and passion. It was proposed that crime also declined as people moved into adulthood because of the growth of reason with age. Quetelet (p. 55) suggested that there was not sufficient data at that time to test his biological explanation for the age distribution of crime.

It is now 180 years later, and we know much more about how various human factors such as physical and mental capacity change over the life course. It would seem to be an appropriate time to blow the dust off Quetelet's biological explanation for the age distribution of crime to see if it has any validity. Biological explanations for crime have gained increased acceptance in recent years (Walsh, & Beaver, 2009; Wright, Tibbetts, & Daigle, 2008), and no longer have the stigma that they once did (Rafter, 2008).

The age distribution of arrests has since become known as the "age crime curve" (Farrington, 1986). There has been an increasing level of interest in the age distribution of crime over the past 50 years, beginning with discussions of age and crime by Greenberg (1977), Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983), and Farrington (1986). Although there has been considerable

speculation on the reasons for the age crime curve, proposed empirical solutions have been limited. This paper fills a need for further exploration of the proposition that developmental changes in strength and mental ability cause the age crime curve.

Figure 1: Total Arrests by Age and Gender for United States from 1996-2006 (NIBRS, 2012)

The age-crime curve is one of the most well established facts about the distribution of crime in the population (Farrington, 1986, Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983). See Figure 1 for the plots of separate age-crime curves for males and females found by calculating the total number of arrests by age and gender in the United States for the eleven years from 1996 to 2006. It is apparent that the general shapes of the age crime curves for males and females are similar, but that the peak level of crime at age 18 is about four times higher for males than females. To give some perspective on relative numbers, the percentage of male arrested at age 18 is about 6% of all males, and the average level of crimes for females at age 18 is about 5% of all females. Note that crime appears to be nonexistent for the very young and very old, but this is an artifact of the scale differences. Although the numbers of arrests are very low at the ends of the scale, there were non-zero arrest data that ranged from ages 1 to 98.

Although criminologists have been discussing the age crime curve since the 1970s (Farrington, 1986; 1990; Gove, 1985; Greenberg, 1977; 1985; Greenberg, & Larkin, 1985; Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983; Steffensmeier, & Allan, 2000; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998), there does not seem to be a generally accepted explanation for the age distribution of crime (Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Sweeten, Piquero, & Steinberg, 2013). It would seem that this is a serious oversight (Loeber, 2012; Osgood, 2005;2012). Without an adequate explanation for the causes of the population distribution of crime by age, it is difficult to identify the between individual differences in normal levels of within-individual variation in crime over the life course. Determining the probable cause of the age crime curve is a conceptual problem that must be solved if progress is to be made in a life course model of criminal activity. If, as this model appears to suggest, physical and mental capacities cause changes in the probability of arrest over the life course, measures of the individual levels of these capacities should be included in any life course studies of crime.

This paper presents a test of Quetelet's biological explanation of the age crime curve. Quetelet proposed that population changes in physical strength, passion, and mental capacity (reason) over the life course cause the distinctive shape of the age crime curve. Since it would appear that passion and reason are both directly related to mental capacity, a simplified model that only includes life course trajectories of physical and mental capacity will be tested. If additional data on the level of passion can be found, this could be added to the model later.

From an examination of the issues involved, it would appear that increased physical strength or diminished mental capacity are unlikely to cause crime directly. It would appear that the issue is one of capacity. A certain level of physical capacity is required for many crimes to be committed. Therefore, given that strength should be directly related to the level of crime, it

seems reasonable that crime increases with increases in physical strength in adolescence and decreases with the declines in strength as people age as Quetelet suggested.

Also, since mental capacity tends to increase with age, it would not seem unreasonable to expect that people would be less likely to commit crimes as intelligence increases due to brain development. There is a well established negative relationship between mental ability and criminal behavior, with crime decreasing as mental ability increases (Wilson, & Hernstein, 1985; Hirschi, & Hindelang, 1977). Given the fact that crime is inversely related to mental capacity, criminal behavior should decrease as intelligence increases from birth to middle age due to increases in brain capacity with age.

An examination of the timing of the growth and decline of physical and mental abilities over the life course provides a challenge to the theorist however. It will be shown that physical capacity peaks in the mid-twenties, and mental capacity peaks in the mid thirties. Crime starts decreasing at about age 18, well before the peak in strength. It would appear that crime should have continued to grow into the mid twenties. In the tests done in this article, it would appear that under certain circumstances, the timing of the growth trajectories of physical and mental capacities can produce the age crime curve. This would appear to provide some support for Quetelet's biological explanation for the age crime curve.

The data suggests that the age crime curve is a cumulative probability distribution that is driven by changes in strength and brain capacity over the life course. There would appear to be three primary patterns in the age distribution of crime, a childhood pattern from 0-19, a young adult pattern from 19-35, and an older adult pattern from 36-98. As the body gains strength in childhood and adolescence from ages 0-18, and the brain has not yet developed full control, crime increases. From age 19-35, the brain continues to develop, while levels of strength change

slowly. This results in a sharp drop in crime from 19 to 30, followed by a gradual flattening of the age crime curve from 30 to 40. As strength starts to decline more rapidly in old age, crime starts to drop off again.

The methods used in this paper fall under the heading of logical inference and exploratory data analysis (EDA; Behrens, 1997; Tukey, 1977). A thorough analysis of the empirical research on crime as well as an analysis of the research on physical and mental development will be conducted to determine a set of logical inferences that appear to flow from the research. These logical inferences will be used to construct a model designed to explain how life course changes in physical and mental capacities might cause the age crime curve.

In conjunction with an analysis of prior research, exploratory data analysis will also be used. EDA provides a set of techniques for analyzing data that include visual inspection of data and graphical analysis. While the results provided by EDA do not provide the type of empirical evidence that is normally associated with tests of theory, it would seem that graphical methods of analysis are probably all that are possible with the types of population data on strength, mental capacity, and crime that are currently available. The purpose of these analysis is to provide direction for future studies that could explore these hypotheses in more depth.

This article provides several important contributions to the literature on the age crime curve. It will be suggested that the age crime curve is composed of three separate curvilinear trajectories, rather than the two trajectories previously considered. Previous discussions of the age crime curve focus on the fact that crime increases from birth to about age 18 and then decrease from 19 to death. The evidence suggests that there is a separate transition in the age crime curve from 19-35 that also needs to be explained. Using a three phase model of physical strength and mental capacity, A mathematical model of strength and mental capacity will be

developed that shows a high level of ability to predict the age crime curve. It will be demonstrated that the age crime curve appears to be a cumulative probability distribution. The methods used in these analyses do not appear to have been used before in criminology, and so it is possible that they will open up further avenues for research.

The Age Crime Debate

An article by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) appears to have set the stage for much of the later research and discussions on the age distribution of crime. Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) proposed three controversial hypotheses, that have come to be known as (1) the “invariance hypothesis,” (2) the “non-interactive hypothesis,” and (3) the “inexplicability hypothesis” (Britt, 1992; Sweeten, Piquero, and Laurence, 2012; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998).

These three hypotheses were stated by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) as follows,

(1) the age distribution of crime is invariant across social and cultural conditions; (2) theories of crime that do not explicitly attend to age have no logical or empirical obligation to do so and should not be judged by their apparent ability or inability to account for the age effect; (3) the age distribution of crime cannot be accounted for by any variable or combination of variables currently available to criminology; (p. 554)

The biological explanation for the age crime curve proposed by Quetelet is compatible with all three hypothesis. If there is a biological explanation for the age crime curve, the curve should not vary by social and cultural conditions, sociological theories of crime should not have to explain the biological changes across the life course, and sociological variables should not be able to explain biological development. The evidence suggests that there is limited support for these three hypotheses.

The invariance hypothesis

Regarding the invariance hypotheses, the evidence suggests that it is important to define exactly what is meant by the term “invariance.” Britt (1992), citing an unpublished paper by Land, McCall, and Cohen (1989), suggests that the invariance of the age crime curve can consist of either parametric or mathematical forms of invariance. Parametric invariance would require that there is the same mean peak in offending across all cultures. A mathematical form of invariance would simply require that the age-crime curve has the same general mathematical distribution across all cultures. It appears that there is more support for a mathematical form of invariance than there is for parametric invariance.

If the parametric form of invariance were present, there would be a peak in crime at the same mean age across all cultures. This would appear to be an untenable position since the mean age of the peak in criminal activity varies over different time periods and cultures (Farrington, 1986; Greenberg, 1985; 2008; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989; Steffensmeier, & Streifel, 1991). The level of crime also varies widely between countries (United Nations, n.d.), which provides strong evidence that the height of the age crime probably varies between cultures. These data suggest that the parametric form of invariance does not exist.

The possibility that the age crime curve has the same mathematical form in every culture and time period would appear to be a less controversial proposition (Britt, 1992; Farrington, 1986; Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990; Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983; Quetelet, 1831/1984; Shavit, & Rattner, 1988; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989; Steffensmeier, & Streifel, 1991; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998; Zhong, 2005). There would appear to be a “unimodal” structure in the age distribution of crime across all cultures, with a peak in crime in late adolescence.

A mathematical form of invariance is compatible with a biological explanation for the age crime curve. Even though there may be changes between cultures in the mean age that crime peaks, or the level of the peak, it is likely that biological factors would still create a single peak in late adolescence.

There is no general consensus on the exact nature of the mathematical form of the age crime curve. Loeber (2012) suggested that the age crime curve is quadratic or cubic. Others (Blumstein, Farrington, & Moitra, 1985; Moffit, 1993) have suggested that the age crime curve is the combination of multiple offending curves. A review of the literature by Jennings and Reingle (2012) provides support for five separate types of offending trajectories that make up the age crime curve. Telesca Erosheva, Kreager, and Matsueda (2012) suggest that the age-crime curve is unimodal, and tried to replicate it with a Poisson warping regression model. Given that lack of consensus in this area, it would appear that any efforts to derive the mathematical form of the age crime curve would be a step in the right direction.

The current test of Quetelet's biological model is an attempt to provide an explanation for the mathematical form of invariance, which is the invariance of the age crime curve across social and cultural conditions. The model presented here is a departure from past attempts to provide an explanation for the shape of the age crime curve. Although attempts have been made to find mathematical formulas that might explain the rate of crime over the life course (Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, & Visser, 1986; Nagin, & Land, 1993), and theorists have posited that crime desists in adulthood due to developmental processes (Leblanc, & Loeber, 1998; Loeber, & Leblanc, 1990), it does not appear that there has been an attempt to discover the mathematical relationship between crime rates and changes in physical and mental capacity.

The non-interactive hypothesis

The non-interactive hypothesis is that sociological theories of crime do not have to explain the variation in crime rates with age. Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) argued that the reasons that different groups commit varying levels of crime is not related to the reasons that people at different ages commit different levels of crime. It is less clear that this hypothesis is compatible with a biological explanation with the age crime curve. If there are time stable differences in the biological capacities for criminal activity, these could create interactions with sociological variables. For instance, if the time varying rate of mental capacity affects the rates of crime, time stable differences may show up as sociological differences such as socioeconomic status. The present exploration does not take these factors into account.

The inexplicability hypothesis

The inexplicability hypothesis is that sociological variables will not explain the age crime curve. A major test of the inexplicability hypothesis was done by Sweeten, Piquero, and Lauritsen (2013). They included up to 40 variables in a multivariate random effects binomial regression model predicting the level of criminal involvement with age. They used linear and quadratic terms in the model. The sample included subjects that had been convicted of a serious offense from 14 to 18 and followed for several years. They began with a model that included only age, and then added theoretically relevant variables to determine if the age effect could be reduced to zero. If the age variable could be reduced to zero, it would indicate that other sets of variables could explain crime, and thus disprove the inexplicability hypothesis. The age variable could be reduced from explaining 89% of the variation to explaining 21% in the best fitting model. It was suggested that the inexplicability hypothesis could not be disproven completely.

One of the more interesting conclusions was, “The results of our investigation shows that one reason it is so difficult to explain why people stop committing crimes as they get older is that this drop is the result of the combined small effects of many, many factors, and not the result of any one or two specific influences operating alone.” (Sweeten et al., 2013; p. 16) The proposed test of Quetelet’s biological explanation of the age crime curve would appear to refute the conclusion of Sweeten et al. (2013). It would appear that two factors, strength and mental capacity might explain a large portion of the variation in crime rates over the life course.

The current study

The current study will be designed to determine whether population life course trajectories of strength and mental capacity could explain the mathematical form of the age crime curve. This explanation is not designed to explain between individual or within individual changes in crime, although physical strength and mental capacity may affect those differences as well. There are literally hundreds of factors associated with differences in criminal behavior over the life course (Ellis, Beaver, & Wright, 2009), and it would be illogical to suppose that only two factors affect individual differences in criminal activity.

It is also noted that not all crimes follow the same age crime curve (Greenberg, 1985; Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998; Zhong, 2005). Some crimes peak earlier than others, and some peak later. Although the shape of the distribution for individual crimes varies widely, but there is still an overall peak in adolescence for the aggregate level of criminal activity.

There were a number of steps in the development of this biological model of the age crime curve. Some are not intuitive and so there may be some dispute over their validity.

Dispute is welcome. A number of basic propositions will be laid out that have varying levels of empirical and logical support. It is suggested that the inevitable conclusion is that there should be certain relationships between the levels of physical strength and mental capacity and the levels of crime by age over the life course. The techniques used to test the empirical model that will be presented have never been used before to my knowledge, and so their validity is subject to debate. The accuracy of the model is so high however, that the accuracy in itself would provide some reason for debate. How can an empirical model fit the data to a ten thousandth of a decimal point if it has no validity?

In the proposal that follows, Quetelet's biological explanation for the shape of the age crime curve will be tested. In testing this explanation, the developmental trajectories of two biological factors, physical strength and brain maturation, will be used to provide a possible explanation for the shape of the age crime curve.

The development of the biological explanation for the age crime curve will consist of three steps. First, a set of logical propositions related to the age crime curve will be discussed. Second, the dynamics of a general biological explanation for the age crime curve will be explored and some hypotheses will be proposed. Third, a set of predictions will be made and compared with the empirical data on crime.

Some logical propositions

There are several logical propositions that will be made in testing Quetelet's biological explanation for the age crime curve. These propositions are as follows,

- 1) The age crime curve is a population phenomenon.
- 2) The age crime curve must be due to biological factors.
- 3) A single factor biological solution is implausible.

- 4) A two factor biological explanation is the next simplest solution.
- 5) Crimes generally require a certain level of physical capacity.
- 6) Criminal behavior is a poor choice and should be inversely related to mental capacity.
- 5) Crime a social construct, and so analogous behaviors must be considered.
- 6) Rule breaking and aggression decline from birth.
- 7) Criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population
- 8) The age crime curve is a probability distribution.
- 9) There are three separate phases in the age crime curve

The justification for these propositions is discussed below. This will be followed by the presentation of a two factor biological explanation for the age crime curve that addresses these facts. It will be proposed that developmental changes in physical strength interact with developmental changes in the brain to create the age crime curve. A mathematical model will be tested that indicates that there is a strong association between the model and the age crime curve.

The age crime curve is a population phenomenon

The age crime curve is found in the age distribution of arrest rates for the entire population of a country such as the United States (NIBRS, 2012). Some form of the unimodal age crime curve was found in France in the 1800s (Quetelet, 1831/1984), the United States, (NIBRS, 2012), England (Farrington, 1986), and Taiwan (Zhong, 2005). The age crime curve has a similar shape across many periods (Quetelet, 1831/1984; Steffensmeier, & Streifel, 1991), and cultures (Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983). In essence, the age crime curve is most reliably produced when looking at large numbers of people.

Since the age crime curve is a population phenomenon, it cannot be explained by looking solely at subgroups of the population such as criminals. As noted by Durkheim (1895/1938),

crime is a normal fact of human behavior. When Quetelet started looking for the causes of crime, he focused on biological traits that were found in all humans, not just a subset of the population.

The fact that different populations have different age crime curves (Zhong, 2005), crime peaks at different ages for different periods or types of crime (Farrington, 1986; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989), or that subgroups of the population have different age crime curves (Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, & Visher, 1986; Ezell, & Cohen, 2005; Glueck, & Glueck, 1950; Jennings, & Reingle, 2012; Moffitt, 1993; Wolfgang, Figlio, & Sellin, 1972) does not negate the fact that there is a general similarity in the age crime curve between populations. Criminal propensity can vary from highly criminal to noncriminal in different groups of people in the population (Moffitt, 1993), but if one limits the analysis of the personal characteristics of the portion of the population that commits the greatest proportion of criminal acts, factors that affect the rest of the population would be ignored.

This is not meant to be a disparagement of attempts to study the age crimes curves of criminals (Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, & Visher, 1986; Sweeten, Piquero, & Lauritsen, 2013). Such efforts are badly needed. It is just that efforts to study criminals are unlikely to provide an insight into the distribution of crime with age for “normal” people.

Any theory that provides an explanation of the age crime curve must use population parameters that vary over time for the entire population as part of the explanation. Whatever is occurring that causes the age crime curve is occurring at the population level for everyone in every population at approximately the same time. The dynamics of the developmental trajectories of the underlying factors that are causing the age crime curve must be identified at

the population level in order to explain the generality of the age crime curve across so many locations and time periods.

The age crime curve must be due to biological factors

One of the primary theses of this paper is that the shape of the age crime curve must be due to biological factors. There is considerable support for the invariance hypothesis that the mathematical form of the age crime curve is fairly consistent across cultures and time periods (Britt, 1992; Farrington, 1986; Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990; Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983; Quetelet, 1831/1984; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989; Steffensmeier, & Streifel, 1991; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998; Zhong, 2005). These data provide strong evidence that the cause of the age crime curve is biological rather than social. This is not meant to indicate that social factors may not affect the shape of the age crime curve. However social factors must play a secondary role by providing variation from the norm.

Stolzenberg, and D'Alessio (2008) examined the relationship between co-offending and the age-crime curve and found that co-offending did not appear to have a relationship with the age crime curve. This provides support for the hypothesis that social factors are not causal factors determining the shape of the age crime curve.

Therefore, given that the age-crime curve is found across all cultures, for both sexes, and for various crime types, it is implausible that a sociological explanation is going to provide an adequate explanation of this phenomenon. If sociology cannot explain the age crime curve, then there must be some type of biological explanation.

A single factor biological solution is implausible

In searching for a biological explanation of the age crime curve, It appears that no one single biological factor will be adequate (cf. Gove, 1985). If the shape of the age crime curve shown in Figure 1 is examined, it is clear that the transition from increasing to decreasing crime at about age 18 cannot be due to a single factor. The rapid acceleration in offending behavior seen in adolescence is followed by an almost equally rapid deceleration in offending behavior as the population enters early adulthood. It seems clear that there is no single biological factor that changes that quickly in the population, and so a single factor solution is not possible.

Solutions to the age crime curve such as those proposed by Steinberg (2012) that suggest that changes in brain development alone causes acceleration and declines in criminal activity are untenable, since the speed of changes is not that rapid and the timing of the changes is unequal between individuals. Not every person suddenly develops a brain change exactly at the age of seventeen. There are also slight timing differences in brain development between males and females, and the age crime curves are essentially the same for both sexes (See Figure 2 below). Population level changes in any single biological trait are not as rapid as the acceleration and decline seen in the age crime curve. This means that an interaction between at least two biological factors is needed to explain the age crime pattern.

An age crime theory should be parsimonious

If a minimum of two factors are needed, more than two factors should be avoided if possible. The principle of Ockham's razor is that the simplest solution that fits the facts should be selected. Sober (1981) called Ockham's principle the "principle of parsimony." Any theory of the age crime curve should use as few variables as it possible. The age crime curve is a population process. Although individual differences in the levels of crime are influenced by thousands of factors (Ellis, Beaver, & Wright, 2009), since the age crime curve is a population

phenomenon, one should not need thousands of factors to explain the shape of the age crime curve. It should be possible, through logical examination of population biological dynamics, to find a few simple facts of human development that explain the age relationship between biological changes in the person and the population crime rate by age.

Crimes generally require a certain level of physical capacity

Quetelet (1831) argued that crimes vary over the life course with physical strength. Van De Warker (1875) suggested that the reason crime rates are lower for women is that they have lower levels of physical strength. The evidence presented for this conclusion was that women commit violent crimes, which presumably require more strength, at a rate of 1/6 that of men, while women committed thefts at a rate of 1/4 that of men. While other explanations may account for this difference, difference in physical strength could provide part of the reason that women commit fewer crimes.

Several authors (Adams, 1997; Gove, 1985; Greenberg, 1977) have suggested that physical strength is one factor that affects the level of crime with age. Crimes require a certain level of physical strength and agility, and this factor is changing over the life span. Therefore, it would be reasonable to assume that the amount of strength seen at different ages is related in some fashion to the level of crime committed. Strength levels in the population increase in childhood, remain relatively stable in young adulthood, and then decrease in old age.

Gove (1985) had indicated that the rise and fall of strength is one factor that could play a part in creating the age crime curve. Steffensmeier and Allen (1995) suggested that strength data by age collected by Montoye (1975) indicates that physical strength does not start declining until about age 40 and therefore, declines in strength with age cannot explain the sharp reduction in crime at age 18, as was suggested by Gove (1985). However, this data does not disprove a

theory that would propose that the increases in strength from birth to age 18 could cause an increase in crime rates during that period.

In the case of aggression, an increase in strength would explain why, even though overall levels of aggression decline as children age, adolescents are found to be committing more crimes of aggression from 10 to 18. Two 10 year olds hitting each other do little damage, and the police are generally not called to arrest them. Two seventeen year olds hitting each other can do considerable damage and are more likely to be charged with assault. Even though total levels of aggressive behavior are declining from age 10 to 17, there is much more violent crime reported at age 17 than at age 10.

Crime a social construct, and so analogous behaviors must be considered

Crime is a social construct. Crime is defined by the society that a person lives in. Things that are considered crimes vary by the age of the person. For instance, two year old children regularly bite, hit, and kick each other. These behaviors are not considered crimes for two year olds, and yet they would be considered crimes if an adult performed them. Therefore, any theory that attempts to explain the age crime curve must consider how analogous behaviors vary over the life course.

The two analogous behaviors examined in this paper are rule breaking and aggression. Crime is a form of rule breaking. Crime is a violation of the rules of society. Aggression is also a form of rule breaking. Extremely aggressive acts are sanctioned by the laws in most cultures, although less aggressive acts are not. Crimes are serious violations of the rules of society, and include serious acts of aggression. By looking at how analogous behaviors change over the life course, it is possible to develop explanations that explain why crimes increase from age 10 to 18 while the levels of rule breaking and aggression are declining during that period.

Rule breaking and aggression decline from birth

It may seem counterintuitive when examining the age crime curve, but at the populations level, rule breaking and aggression decline from birth. Logically, if we consider the infant, we find that they do not understand what rules are and do not obey any rules other than those that are biologically imprinted. Children begin life as asocial beings. Therefore, the age of highest rule breaking is at age zero.

Children at the age of two are called the terrible twos for very good reasons. Two year old children are highly self centered and generally are trying to get everyone else to do what they want, rather than doing what others want. With some exceptions, the population pattern is that most children are taught to follow the rules as they age, and continue to be better at following the rules into adulthood.

It would appear that rule following behavior is increasing throughout the entire life course. Since crimes are simply formal rules, and rule breaking began to decline at birth, there must be something other than the cause of the decline in rule breaking that explains the apparent increase in criminal activity (formal rule breaking) during adolescence.

Several sources confirm the general declines in rule breaking with age. Elliot et al. (1983) examined self report data on criminal activity in adolescence from the National Youth Survey. They found that the prevalence of many crimes was declining from age 11. The incidence of other types of crimes increased during that period, leading to an apparent increase in the overall crime rate with age.

Lauritsen (1998) analyzed longitudinal self report data for criminal activity by adolescents and found that no matter which age from 11 to 17 was used as a starting point, the level of criminal activity declined with age. This data supports the hypothesis that rule breaking is declining at the same time that crime rates appear to be increasing.

Steinberg and Monahan (2007) analyzed age differences in resistance to peer influence using a measure of resistance that was independent of likelihood of engaging in anti-social behavior. They found that resistance to peer influence increases from age 10 through age 23. These data suggest that anti-social peers should have less and less influence with age.

Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) posited that criminal behavior is more likely if people have low self-control. A review of the research by Pratt and Cullen (2000) provides some support for the theory that low self-control is positively related to criminal activity and analogous behaviors. Turner and Piquero (2002) analyzed the level of self-control within individual adolescents and found that levels of low self-control showed a steady pattern of decreasing levels from ages 9 to 19, which suggests that rule breaking should be decreasing during that period because there is a positive relationship between low self-control and rule breaking.

Similarly, in addition to the declines in rule breaking, aggression appears to be declining from birth as well. Numerous studies suggest that population levels of aggression decline from a young age (Barker et al., 2006; Bongers, Koot, van der Ende, & Verhulst, 2004; Brame, Nagin, & Tremblay, 2001; Broidy, et al., 2003; Nagin & Tremblay, 1999; 2005). While there are generally small groups of children that maintain high levels of aggression or have increases in aggression, the majority of children are exhibiting low stable or declining levels of aggression from a very young age. In general, most people become less aggressive as they age.

These data provide a paradox. Since aggression and rule breaking appear to be declining, something other than an increase in aggression and rule breaking must be causing the increased contact with the criminal justice system. The solution to this paradox requires a reanalysis of what is being reported in official crime rates. It would appear that crime is increasing from 10 to 18, but overall levels of rule breaking and aggression are decreasing. The explanations for this

paradox seems to be that either the seriousness of the offenses committed or the official responses to breaking the rules, or both offense seriousness and sanction levels are increasing with age. Acts that are not considered crimes at age 10 are being considered crimes at age 18 either because of the greater strength of the person committing the acts, or the fact that people are more likely to be charged for their actions. It would appear to be difficult to determine which is occurring.

It seems likely that the types of activities performed are changing from childhood to adulthood. This is called heterotypic continuity (Wright, Tibbetts, & Daigle, 2008). With heterotypic continuity, biting at age two turns into hitting at age 18. It is possible that rule breaking can be declining at the population level from ages 0-18, while appearing to increase from 0-18 when measured as criminal acts. Therefore, analogous rule breaking behaviors must be considered when examining the age crime curve. When they are, it appears that rule breaking is declining as adolescents age rather than increasing.

Criminal behavior is a poor choice

While it is possible to come up with exceptions, in general, crimes are highly irrational acts that result in little benefit for those committing them (cf. Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990). Criminal activity has many unwanted potential consequences. Any solution that is proposed for the reasons that crimes are committed should reflect the fact that criminal behavior tends to be a poor choice and criminal acts would not be committed if the person was acting rationally.

The relationship between mental ability and criminal behavior is well documented (Hirschi, & Hindelang, 1977; Wilson, & Herrnstein, 1985). In general, people who commit crimes tend to have lower levels of intelligence than those who do not commit crimes. Wilson

and Herrnstein (1985) found that criminal offenders have an average of an 8 point lower IQ when compared to non-criminals.

One of the more obvious biological changes that occurs in human development is the development of decision making ability over time. Quetelet suggested that reason increases with age. Children have little ability to make choices at birth and develop this ability over time. There appears to be a steady gain in the ability of human beings to process information that continues from birth into middle age. The proposition that maturation is a possible reason for a decline in criminal activity was proposed by Glueck, and Glueck (1950; p. 274). In a review of possible reasons for the decline in crime with age, Loeber and Farrington (2012) discuss “brain maturation” as a possible reason.

Any discussion of brain maturation must deal with the fact that the brain is maturing from birth. Why do arrest rates increase in adolescence if the brain is becoming better at making decisions? One would expect a decrease in rule breaking, and not an increase. As mentioned previously, rule breaking and aggression are decreasing from birth. This is exactly what should happen if rule breaking is a poor choice and the apparatus for making choices, the brain, was improving over time. If overall levels of rule breaking are decreasing from ages 10 to 18, some other reason must be found for the apparent reverse effect of crime increasing in adolescence.

Theoretical explanations of the age crime curve that fail to account for the actual decline in rule breaking from birth are suspect. For instance, Steinberg (2012) fails to take the decline in rule breaking in adolescence into account when arguing that crime increases because adolescents simply do not have the cognitive ability to make decisions like adults. While this is partially true, he fails to account for the fact that cognitive ability is increasing from birth, and rule breaking should be declining. Steinberg (2012) argues that brain changes cause the increase in

crime seen in adolescence, and this would not seem to be the case given that aggression and rule breaking are declining from birth. The argument that brain development causes rapid increases and then rapid decreases in crime seems to be contrary to the evidence because brain development is a slow process and changes are not so sudden as to cause the rapid acceleration and deceleration in crime seen at the transition period around age 18.

Criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population

It is proposed that criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population. While there is not appear to be a great deal of data to support this claim, there are some discussions on the topic. Clarke and Weisburd (1990) analyzed data from the National Youth Survey that suggests that deviance is more normally distributed when minor forms of deviance are included in the analysis. However, there is a small minority of offenders that tends to skew the deviance distribution in a positive direction. This is consistent with the findings of Wolfgang, Figlio, and Sellin (1972). Clarke and Weisburd (1990) suggest however, that official reports of deviance such as arrest rates tend to indicate a more normal shape to the distribution of deviance in the population. Since the current study is using arrest data, the proposition that criminal propensity is normally distributed may be warranted. In another study, Wikström (2009) reports that criminal propensity was normally distributed in a random sample of adults assessed in the Peterborough Community Survey. This provides additional support for the proposition that criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population.

The age crime curve is a probability distribution

If one normalizes that age crime curve by turning the number of crimes ate each age into a percentage, the age crime curve becomes a probability distribution that provides the probability

of arrest at each age. The sum of all of the individual probabilities adds to one. For any arrest, it is possible to calculate the odds of arrest. For instance, if someone is arrested, it can be calculated that there is a 6% chance that they are 18 years old. While this might seem to be a rather useless piece of information, it will become a key part of the model that is proposed.

There are three separate phases in the age crime curve

Previous discussions of the age crime curve have focused on the fact that there are two general trends in the age distribution of crime. Crime increases from childhood to young adulthood and then decreases until death. It is proposed that a two part solution is an oversimplification and that there are actually three phases in the age crime curve. There is a childhood phase from birth to 18, a young adult phase from 19-45, and an older adult phase from 46 to death. The phases are shown in the plots shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Percentages of Crimes by Age for Males and Females (Males = 100%, Females = 100%, Source - NIBRS)

In Figure 2, the United States arrest data from 1996 to 2006 for males and females (NIBRS, 2012) has been transformed into two separate probability distributions. It is clear that the general shape of the curves is fairly similar for males and females. The more obvious transition is seen at age 18, where there is a sharp reversal in the probability of arrest. Crime then declines until about age 30 and then there is another transition phase between ages 30 and 45. These two transitions provide important clues about the processes leading to the age crime curve.

The childhood phase runs from birth to about age eighteen as the child grows from an infant to an adult. There appear to be two sections in this curve, but further analysis will suggest that this is one distinct pattern. There is a period of almost no crime from birth to about age 8 or 9, and then a period of almost linearly increasing crime from about age 10 to 18. It appears on first examination that the childhood pattern is an exponential growth curve. A later analysis will reveal that this is a more complex cumulative probability distribution from 0-18.

The young adult phase covers the period from 19 to 45. There appears to be a deceleration in the rate of crime that starts rapidly at age 19 and then slowly dissipates in the age range between 30 and 40. The rate of deceleration then starts to increase again at about age 40. The age of 45 is suggested as a cutoff for this range. This deceleration curve is not an exponential curve and it appears to have some interesting properties. This trajectory either fits a cubic model or two quadratic trajectories with the model split at about age 35.

The older adult phase covers the period from 46 to death. There appears to be an exponential deceleration in the rate of crime that starts in the previous section at age 40. Although an initial examination suggests an exponential deceleration curve, further analysis will indicate that this also fits a cumulative probability model.

It will be suggested that these three phases in the age crime curve each require separate explanations. It will be argued that the life course development of physical strength and brain capacity provides a plausible explanation for these three curves. This explanation appears to provide a strong fit with the known facts on the age distribution of crime.

Tying it all together: A two factor biological solution to the age crime curve

The question becomes, is there a simple explanation that uses population level factors related to the biological development of the physical and mental capacities of the individual that would explain the crime and analogous behaviors that produce the age crime curve? It appears that the answer to this question is yes. If the population dynamics of physical strength and brain development are combined, the age crime curve is the result. While this result does not seem immediately intuitive, a thorough examination will reveal that this solution has some merit.

The following argument consists of two primary sets of proposals. The first proposal is that the age crime curve actually consists of three separate curves. There is an acceleration curve in childhood from birth to about age 18, there is a deceleration curve and then an acceleration curve in young adulthood from about 19 to 45, and there is another deceleration curve from about age 46 to death.

The second proposal is that two things are required for a crime to be committed, the physical capacity to commit the crime and a deficiency in the decision making capacity required to prevent the commission of the crime. If there is insufficient physical capacity, or the person has sufficient common sense, crimes generally do not occur. The essence of the theory proposed below is that population timing of developmental changes in physical strength and brain capacity cause the age crime curve.

Changes in Strength with Age

One of the hypotheses of this explanation is that crimes do not occur unless there is sufficient physical strength to commit them. The general pattern seen in the population age strength trajectory is displayed in Figure 3 below. The model shown in Figure 3 is a hypothetical model that is not based on empirical data. The assumptions used in this model are that, at the population level, strength starts at near zero at birth, climbs linearly over most of the childhood years and then peaks in the mid 20s, remains relatively flat until age 40, and then declines linearly with age. While there is not a longitudinal study of strength that covers the entire life course, Malina, Bouchard, and Bar-Or (2004; pp. 218-223) document an almost linear increase in strength from preschool to about age 18, so this part of the model should be relatively accurate.

Figure 3: Hypothesized Strength Level by Age

Figure 4 gives an example of the changes in strength that might be found by using actual data. As shown in Figure 4, using data adapted from Sterken (2001) the average predicted speed correction factors for race distances from 5K to the marathon for ages 1 to 95 follow a similar

pattern to the hypothesized pattern in Figure 3. If we assume that running speed is a proxy for strength, we can use this as an approximation for the level of strength by age.

There are some differences between the hypothesized and actual strength data that are worth noting. Strength does not start at zero, as suggested by the hypothesized model. Sterken's (2001) data suggests that one year old racers are moving at 40% of peak velocity, which seems unlikely and suggests that there may be some problems with the model used in that analysis. These problems are minor and should not affect the discussions that follow. The main point is that strength follows a curvilinear trajectory over the life course with near linear increases in youth, peak strength levels occurring somewhere in the mid 20s, and near linear decreases in strength for older adults.

Figure 4: Estimated Speed Correction Factor by Age (Sterken, 2001)

If the strength pattern is compared with the pattern seen in the age crime curve, it would appear that the increases in strength found from age ten to 18 closely mirror the linear increases in crime found during that age period. Similarly, the declines in strength seen from age 35 to 98

also mirror the declines in crime from ages 35 to 98. While it would appear that the strength curve matches the general direction taken by crime rates seen in the first and third section of the age crime curve, the linear nature of the changes in strength do not match the nonlinear changes in the crime rate. This problem will be addressed later.

Changes in Brain Function with Age

It is hypothesized that the avoidance of criminal behavior requires a certain level of decision-making capacity. In that case, rule breaking should be inversely related to the level of decision making capacity. As brain function increases, rule breaking should decrease.

For the purposes of this discussion, it is proposed that the decision-making capacity of the brain starts at a low point and grows over the life course, eventually peaking at about age 30-35, where it flattens out and then begins declining. A hypothetical approximation of the developmental trajectory of the growth of the decision-making capacity of the brain over the life course is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Hypothesized Level of Brain Capacity with Age

The model in Figure 5 is supported by data collected by Lehman (1953) that shows the intellectual productivity levels for various professions as people age. Functional capacity increases until about age 30 to 40 and then starts to decline in old age. The level of intellectual capacity does not decline to zero in old age.

The suggestion that there was a connection between brain capacity and the age crime curve is not new. Kanazawa (2003) analyzed productivity data for 280 scientists and found that productivity peaked at age 30. Peaks in other types of productivity were found between 35 to 45. In the discussion of the results for productivity, it was noted that crime also peaks and then declines. The fact that both intellectual activity and crime both peak was referred to as the crime-genius connection. The problem with Kanazawa's (2000) arguments is that crime peaks about 10-15 years before intellectual achievement. It will be argued here that the increase in productivity between age 20 to 35 is caused by the same factors that cause the decrease in crime during that period. The model proposed here is that there is an inverse crime-genius connection.

Changes in the Level of Rule Breaking with Age

It will be proposed that the level of rule breaking is inversely related to the brain's capacity to make decisions. If this is true, we should be able to invert the pattern seen in Figure 5, and the level of rule breaking would follow a trajectory similar to that shown in Figure 6. Rule breaking would be high in infancy and decline with age until about age 30 to 35. Note that if the proposition that rule breaking is inversely related to mental capacity is true, the model predicts that at some point as people age, the level of rule breaking should start to increase again.

It should be noted that in the graph, rule breaking is shown to decrease to zero, which does not happen at age 30 to 35. The zero point simply suggests a minimum level of influence on rule breaking due to brain capacity. The general idea presented is that, if rule breaking is

inversely related to brain capacity, a pattern similar to that shown in Figure 6 should be seen in the level of rule breaking over the life course.

Figure 6: Hypothesized Level of Rule Breaking by Age

Combining Strength and Brain Capacity Curves Together in a Z-score Model

How do strength and brain capacity combine to create the age crime curve? It will be suggested that changes in strength and brain capacity creates changes in the Z-score representing the cumulative probability of committing a crime. The logic behind this model came from visualizing what might occur to the Z-score of a criminal propensity distribution if criminal propensity was normally distributed.

The basic Z-score model is shown in Figure 7 below. At various ages the Z-score is either increasing or decreasing. In the example shown in Figure 7, at age 5, the Z-score for the level of strength and brain capacity is -3.96 and increasing. The probability of arrest at age five should be the value of the cumulative probability in a normal distribution for a Z-score of -3.96. This number should be very low since most five-year-old children are not strong enough to commit

serious crimes, even though they break many rules. If a linear increase in the Z-score with age occurs, at age 10, the Z-score increases to -2.77. There is a larger cumulative probability of arrest than at age 5, but the total probability of arrest is still low. At age 18, the Z-score increases to -1.55. At age 18, the probability of committing a crime is about 6%, or 6/100ths of the total probability of someone committing a crime at any age. After age 18, as age increases, the Z-score moves back to the left. At age 55, the Z-score is back at the 10-year-old level, and at age 84, the Z-score is at the 5-year-old level.

Figure 7: Probability of Arrest as Age Increases using a Z-Score Model

With this model, the issue then becomes trying to figure out how the Z-score for the criminal propensity probability will change by age. A simple linear model will be proposed. Strength will be considered a risk factor and brain capacity a protective factor. Therefore, the proposed formula for the Z-score is $Z(\text{crime, age}) = F(\text{strength, age}) - G(\text{brain capacity, age})$. Where $F(\text{strength, age})$ is some linear transformation of the mean strength level, and $G(\text{brain capacity, age})$ is a linear transformation of brain capacity.

If linear trajectories for strength and brain capacity are assumed, the following scenario could be imagined. If there was a 5 unit per year increase in the Z-score from 0-18 due to increases in strength, and a 2 unit decrease per year in the Z-score from 0-18 due to increases in brain capacity, the Z-score should rise from near zero at birth at a linear rate of $5 - 2$ units, or 3 units per year until age 18. At that point, the hypothetical Z-score would be 54 units.

The number 54 would not be a number that could be used as a Z-score. If we wanted to use this Z-score with a standard normal probability distribution, the number 54 would have to be transformed by dividing by a constant and subtracting by another constant to get it into an actual range for a standard normal distribution

It would be difficult to determine the relative amounts of change in the Z-score that is contributed by strength and brain capacity using this process. For instance, strength could increase at 6 units per year, and brain capacity could increase at 3 units, and the resulting increase in the Z-score would still be 3 units per year, just like when strength was increasing by 5 units, and brain capacity was increasing at 2 units. However, this problem aside, the proposed linear Z-score model presents a plausible and testable mathematical model for the process occurring with the Z-scores for the age crime probability distribution.

It will be more important to determine the hypothetical mathematical form of the Z-score distribution if it is a function of strength and brain capacity. It should be possible to do so since the relative changes in strength and brain capacity are well known linear trajectories in childhood from 0-18, and in older adults from 46-98.

Since, strength peaks in the mid twenties and brain capacity peaks in the mid thirties, it would seem clear that in the period from 0-18, strength must be increasing at a faster rate than brain capacity. Since both strength and brain capacity are increasing linearly, there should be a

linear increase in the Z-score. To help with the visualization process, the hypothetical trajectories of strength and rule breaking from birth to age 18 are shown in Figure 8. If strength is increasing linearly from 0-18, which leads to an increase in the capacity for crime, and brain capacity is also increasing linearly at a slightly lower rate, then the Z-score by age, which is proposed to be $F(\text{strength, age}) - G(\text{brain capacity, age})$, should increase linearly as well at some rate that is less than the increase in the rate of growth in strength.

Figure 8: Hypothesized Z-score Trajectory Derived from Levels of Strength and Brain Capacity from Birth to 18.

The Z-score model for the likelihood of crime decreasing from age 46-98 should be the reverse of the model for 0-18. In the 46-98 age range, strength is decreasing and brain capacity is decreasing, and it is proposed that crime should decrease at a linear rate as strength declines and brain function declines. In that scenario, the likelihood of committing a crime should decline linearly over time.

The Z-score model for the 19-45 year old range is more complex. Strength is peaking in the mid 20s and brain function is peaking in the mid 30s. The combination of these two curves

created by subtracting brain capacity from strength looks something like that shown in Figure 9 below. These curves are not drawn to scale as they tend to look like straight lines at normal scales. If brain capacity levels are subtracted from the strength levels, the Z-score trajectory from 19-45 should be a declining S shaped curve.

Figure 9: Hypothetical Z-score Trajectory Derived from a Combination of Strength and Brain Capacity from 19-45

Using the strength-brain capacity model for the Z-score trajectory results in the Z-score trajectory shown in Figure 10. There is a linear increase in the Z-scores from 0-18, followed by an S shaped section from 19-45, and then an almost linear decrease in the Z-scores from 46-98. This model is shown in relative units. The actual Z-scores would all be negative for the age crime curve. The important point to consider is that the mathematical form of the Z-score model predicted by the actual age crime curve if the strength-brain capacity relationship is accurate would be as shown.

Figure 10: Hypothetical Z-score Trajectory for the Strength-Brain Capacity Model

Testable hypotheses

The preceding model relies on several assumptions. It is assumed that strength is increasing linearly from 0-18, peaking in the mid 20s, remaining relatively flat through the 30s and 40s and then decreasing from 46-98 in an almost linear fashion. Rule breaking is inversely related to brain capacity, and brain capacity is increasing linearly from 0-18, peaking in the mid 30s, at which time it gradually starts to decrease until brain capacity is decreasing from 46-98 in an almost linear fashion. The intersection of strength and rule breaking capacity is a straight line from 0-18 that rises at something less than would be expected if brain capacity were not increasing. The hypothesis for the following analyses is that the combined strength-brain capacity effect should be a linear increase in the Z-score for a criminal propensity normal curve from 0-18, a curvilinear decrease in the Z-score from 19-45, and a linear decrease in the Z-score from 46-98. There should be three sections to the age crime curve, and this model should be able to fit them all. Finally, realistic models for strength and brain capacity should be able to create the age crime curve.

Data and Measures

The age crime curve data used in this article was obtained from the United States National Incident Reporting System (NIBRS, 2012). The arrests in the U.S. for the 11 year period from 1996 through 2006 were downloaded by age, gender, race, and offense category. The data used was limited to age and gender data. The sum of offenses for all 11 years was created for each age. The percentages of offences by age were then computed for both males and females by dividing by the total number of male and female offenses respectively.

Strength and brain capacity measures used to infer the linear trajectories are inferred from a number of sources. There does not appear to be a population level study of either strength or brain functioning that indicates how either changes at the population level over the entire life course. This requires a system of piecing together information. The physical strength and mental capacity curves are a proposed estimate derived from a number of sources.

Malina, Bouchard, and Bar-Or (2004; pp. 218-223) document that the level of strength appears to increase approximately linearly from birth to age 18. Sterken (2001) compiled speed correction data by age for 11 distances from 5K to the marathon for males and females. The speed correction data is used as a proxy for strength.

The dynamic development of intellectual capacity has been studied in a number of ways. Lehman (1953) examined how intellectual productivity varied in a number of professional occupations such as chemistry, philosophy, music, art etc. The general finding was that the level of intellectual capacity peaked somewhere between the ages of 30 to 40. The plot used in the examples were generated from the age crime curve itself. While this plot may be due to other factors, it is approximately representative of the general trend for intellectual development found in other measures.

Procedure

The procedures used in these analyses begin with exploratory data analyses (EDA) using graphical methods as per the suggestions Hartwig, and Dearing (1979). The basic outline of the EDA method was specified by Behrens (1997).

This tradition of EDA can be loosely characterized by (a) an emphasis on the substantive understanding of data that address the broad question of "what is going on here?" (b) an emphasis on graphic representations of data; (c) a focus on tentative model building and hypothesis generation in an iterative process of model specification, residual analysis, and model respecification; (d) use of robust measures, reexpression, and subset analysis; and (e) positions of skepticism, flexibility, and ecumenism regarding which methods to apply. (pp. 131-132)

The basic structure of the age crime curve is apparent from a close examination of the frequency distribution. In addition to the more obvious transition at around age 18, there is also a transition in the mid 30s. This suggested a three-part solution.

The issues with strength and intelligence curves are a bit more complex. While there is no one data set that provides a plot of strength or intelligence curves over the life course, one can construct a general picture by looking at the results from several datasets.

As per suggestions by Behrens (1997), once a hypothesis is generated through exploratory data analysis (EDA), the researcher can use confirmatory data analysis (CFA) to verify the results found. A variety of statistical techniques were used to rule out some solutions and confirm others. Some of the methods used in the analyses that followed required a repeated refinement of manual techniques in Excel as well as repeated tests with statistical analyses software (SPSS, 2009).

Most of the models generated in this test were built in Excel. Two functions, the NormSInv() function, and the NormSDist() functions were used to convert from percentages to Z-scores, and from Z-scores to percentages. Various linear and nonlinear functions were built by summing values over the age distribution from 0-98.

Results and Discussion

Four sets of tests were conducted. The first test was of a linear Z-score model. A linear model was constructed that created linear sets of Z-Scores from 0-18 and from 46-98. The Z-scores were then plotted using the NormSDist() function in Excel and comparing the graphs generated to the actual age crime curves for males and females from the 1996-2006 NIBRS(2012) data. An iterative procedure was used to fit the models to the age crime curves. Three variables, the slope and intercept of the linear Z-score model, as well as a height factor for the percentages generated by the NormSDist() function, were used to adjust the height and shape of the resulting probability distribution. The data for the 19-45 year old age range was generated manually, and so is not part of the test. The standard error and R^2 values were used as a measure of fit and the model was adjusted to find the minimum standard error.

The second test used SPSS curvefit function to generate standard curve formulas to fit the age crime curves for both males and females. The standard error and R^2 values for the various curves were then compared with those of the Z-score model to determine which model provided the best fit with the age crime curve.

The third test used the NormSInv() function to generate a set of Z-Scores directly from the age crime curve data. The 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98 year sections were then examined using curvefit to determine which model might fit the Z-score distribution by age. It is suggested that a three part model fits the age crime curve better than a single or dual section model.

The fourth test involves the two hypothetical sets of data for strength and brain capacity proposed above. The hypothetical curves are combined using the strength-brain capacity formula suggested above, creating a Z-score distribution, and then the hypothetical Z-score distribution is transformed using the NormSDist() function into a hypothetical age crime curve.

Fitting a linear Z-score model to the age crime curve

The goal of the first test was to determine whether a linear change in Z-scores from 0-18 and from 46-98 could explain why the age crime curve rises slowly in childhood and then starts to accelerate in adolescence, and then falls from 46-98 in a gradual deceleration curve. The following procedures were the same for males and females. An Excel spreadsheet was set up with the following rows.

1. Row 1 represented the ages in the age crime curve, and columns were numbered from 0-98.
2. Row 2 was the Z-score row, which was set up to house the predicted Z-scores from 0-98. Predicted Z-scores were generated by a slope(b)-intercept(a) pair for a line with formula $Z = a + bX$ for ages 0-18 and ages 46-98. Ages 19-46 were fitted manually.
3. Row 3 contained the predicted probability for each Z-score for a normal distribution with mean 0, and standard deviation of 1. Row 3 was populated by using the NormSDist() function with Row 2 as the source for X. The NormSDist() function produces the cumulative probability for a Z-score value assuming a normal distribution with mean 0 and standard deviation of 1.
4. Row 4 contained the cumulative probabilities in Row 3 divided by a constant. The constant was used to adjust the height of the predicted age crime curve.
5. Row 5 contained the actual age crime curve percentages from the average U.S. crime rates from 1996-2006 (NIBRS, 2012) for either males or females.
6. Row 6 contained the difference between the adjusted predicted values (Row 4) and the actual values (Row 5).

7. Row 7 contained the square of the differences between the predicted and actual values (Row 6). The sum of sections of this row provided the sum of the squares that was used to calculate standard errors and R^2 values.
8. A graph was set up to display the predicted values (Row 4) and the actual values (Row 5) of the age crime curve.
9. A control section was set up to house the slope-intercept values for the 0-18 and 46-98 sections, the single divisor for the height adjustment, and the standard errors and R^2 values for each section and the total.

The slope, intercept, and divisor were adjusted for the 0-18 Z-score values until a close match was obtained with the first section of the age crime curve. Z-scores were entered manually for each year from 19-45 to minimize the difference between the calculated probability and the actual age crime curve value. Finally, the slope and intercepts were entered for the age range from 46-98. The results are shown in Figures 12 and 13. Figure 12 shows a plot of the projected and actual age crime curves for males, and Figure 13 shows a plot of the actual and projected age crime curves for females. The fit between the models and the actual age crime curves for both males and females is almost perfect.

Figure 12: Projected and Actual Age Crime Curves for Males

Figure 13: Projected and Actual Age Crime Curves for Females

The model parameters and model fit statistics for males and females are shown in Table 1. These data indicate a very close fit between the hypothetical Z-score model predicted by the strength-brain capacity relationship and the average 1996-2006 age crime curves. The R^2 values are very close to 1, indicating an almost perfect fit between the models and the actual age crime curves. Note that the fit from 19-45 was done manually, so the errors for that range are artificially low.

The predicted values for the 0-18 and 46-96 ranges are very close to the actual values. These data provide strong support for a linear Z-score model for these two age ranges.

Whether this fit is due to levels of strength minus levels of brain capacity would still need to be determined. However, it does appear that crime rates are compatible with the trajectories of strength and brain capacity if a linear trajectory is assumed for these physical factors in the age ranges from 0-18 and from 46-98.

Table 1: Model Parameters and Fit Statistics for the Z-Score Model of the Age Crime Curve

Model	Age Range			
	0-18	19-45	46-98	Total (0-98)
Males				
Intercept (a)	-5.0100		-1.0700	
Slope (b)	.3352		.0760	
Divisor	13.7760			
S.E.	.000478	.000052	.000217	.000528
R^2	.999643	.999997	.998028	.999836
Females				
Intercept (a)	-7.2000		-.9000	
Slope (b)	.5500		.0870	
Divisor	19.4000			
S.E.	.000459	.000002	.000158	.000228
R^2	.999497	1.000000	.995001	.999736

Testing other types of curves against the Z-score model

The Z-score models for males and females appeared to have an excellent fit with the actual age crime curves. It is not clear however, that some other model might not provide as close a match as the Z-score model. Therefore, a number of other models were tested. In the tests that followed, the model fit for various mathematical formulas was tested against the individual age crime curves for the 11 years from 1996-2006, rather than the average curves that had been generated. Testing against the 11 individual annual curves would introduce more variation into the test and this would appear to provide a more accurate test of the model's abilities to predict the age crime curve.

The SPSS curvefit command was used to try to find a formula to fit the entire age crime curve and then the sections of the age crime curve from 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98. All available curve types were tested, which included linear, logarithmic, inverse, quadratic, cubic, compound, power, S, growth, exponential, and logistic fit solutions.

In the full 0-98 year age crime curve model, logarithmic, inverse, power, and S curves had a low R^2 values and so they were not examined further. Compound, growth, exponential, and logistic models all had identical R^2 values, so the growth curve was used to represent that type of curve. The tested curves for the full 0-98 model were reduced to linear, quadratic, cubic, and exponential. The models and R^2 values are shown for the single curve solutions compared to the three part Z-score model in Table 2. It seems clear that the Z-score model is a far more accurate model. Even with the extra variation introduced by comparing the Z-score model to all 11 years, the Z-score model R^2 is .987

Table 2: Single Curve Fit Solutions compared to the Three Part Z-score Model

Model	Formula	a	b ₁	b ₂	b ₃	R ²
Males						
Linear	$Y=a + b_1X$.0242	-.000283			.305
Quadratic	$Y=a + b_1X + b_2X^2$.0185	.000061	-.00000348		.335
Cubic	$Y=a + b_1X + b_2X^2 + b_3X^3$	-.0036	.002672	-.00006908	.00000044	.628
Growth	$Y=e^{(a + b_1X)}$	-3.450	-.072967			.352
Z-score	$Y=a_1*\sum e^{(a_2+b_1X)^2}$.987
Females						
Linear	$Y=a + b_1X$.0242	-.000283			.323
Quadratic	$Y=a + b_1X + b_2X^2$.0183	.000071	-.00000357		.356
Cubic	$Y=a + b_1X + b_2X^2 + b_3X^3$	-.0039	.002690	-.00006937	.00000044	.669
Growth	$Y=e^{(a + b_1X)}$	-3.6174	-.075643			.284
Z-score	$Y=a_1*\sum e^{(a_2+b_1X)^2}$.987

The single solution curves for male arrest rates were plotted along with the three part Z-score model in Figure 14. The other curves do not come close to producing a plot similar to the age crime curve. This suggests that a single curve solution is not possible with simple mathematical models.

Figure 14: Male Single Curve Fit Solutions compared to the Three Part Z-score Model

Two and Three Section Age Crime Curve Models

The single curve solutions had a poor fit to the age crime curve. Two and three part models were tested by dividing the age crime curve data into two sections from 0-18, and 19-98, and three sections, 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98. The SPSS curve fit procedure was run for males and females for both the two section and three section models.

Different curve types had better fits depending on the section being tested. Compound, growth, exponential, and logistic models all had identical R^2 values, so the growth curve was used to represent that type of curve. This left linear, logarithmic, inverse, quadratic, cubic, power, S, and exponential fit solutions. The R^2 values for these models are presented in Table 3 below along with the explained variance for the Z-score model.

Table 3: Explained Variance for Section Models and Total Age Crime Curve Models

Model	0-18	19-45	46-98	19-98	Total (0-98)
Males					
Linear	.744	.758	.541	.727	.305
Logarithmic	.449	.826	.622	.871	.091
Inverse	.173	.883	.702	.951	.003
Quadratic	.967	.878	.837	.943	.335
Cubic	.973	.878	.837	.956	.628
Power	.855	.890	.787	.739	.044
S	.510	.902	.740	.576	.036
Growth	.911	.862	.822	.857	.352
Z-score	.982	.964	.939	.990	.987
Females					
Linear	.766	.777	.512	.760	.323
Logarithmic	.476	.814	.592	.887	.095
Inverse	.187	.841	.671	.933	.003
Quadratic	.933	.811	.805	.953	.356
Cubic	.936	.811	.805	.955	.669
Power	.795	.782	.704	.680	.023
S	.482	.763	.654	.521	.053
Growth	.824	.789	.745	.800	.284
Z-score	.983	.935	.924	.989	.987

These data suggest that the age crime curve is probably some type of cumulative probability function. The other types of mathematical models have fairly high R^2 values, but visual inspection reveals that they do not fit the actual age crime curve data. The highest R^2 values are found with the Z-score model in every case. Note that the section from 19-45 was fit by hand, and so this is not a fair test, but both the 0-18, and 46-98 year old sections are simple linear fit predictions that assume a linear Z-score model in these sections.

The mathematical form of the function for the 0-18 and 46-98 year olds is $Y=a_1*\sum e^{(a_2+b_1X)^2}$. The function in the parenthesis is linear. It is not clear what the function is for the 19-45 year olds. It would appear to be some type of nonlinear function. In the next section, an attempt will be made to determine the mathematical form of all three sections.

Determining the mathematical form of the age crime curve Z-score distribution

The preceding analyses suggested that the age crime curve was some stype of cumulative probability function. If the physical and mental capacities with presumed to affect the Z-score, and the Z-score followed a linear trajectory, it was possible to build a very accurate mathematical model that predicted the arrest rate by age. The NormSDist() function in Excel was used to convert Z-scores to probabilities.

It is also possible to work backward. The NormSInv() function in Excel can convert probabilities to Z-scores. This provides a method for converting the age crime curve to a Z-score distribution without all of the manual fitting required to build the model shown above. It would then be possible to examine each Z-score section to determine what type of mathematical form it had. It would be possible to determine whether the sections from 0-18 and 46-96 were actually linear functions. Creating a Z-score distribution using actual data would also provide a way to try to find the mathematical properties of the Z-score distribution from 19-46.

A simple Excel spreadsheet was created with the age from 0-98 in Row 1, the Age Crime Curve from 1-98 in Row 2, and a Z-score transformation in Row 3 that was created by the NormSInv() function with the values in Row 2 used for X. The Z-score distribution shown in Table 14 was generated. This graph shows the Z-score distribution for males and females. The data for ages 1-2 and from 94-98 appears to not fit the pattern, but the rest of the data seems to indicate a consistent process. Z-scores appear to range from -1.5 to -4.5.

Figure 15: Z-scores for Male and Female Age Crime Curve

One interesting feature of the comparison plots in Figure 15 is that males tend to have slightly higher Z-scores than females before age 10, and then have lower Z-scores from 10-18. This could be due to earlier physical maturation in young male children and earlier puberty and physical maturation by female adolescents.

The Z-Scores for males for the years 1996 to 2006 were plotted for the three sections from 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98 in Figures 16, 17, and 18. Note that the graphs are not all drawn to the same scale. There were missing values in the 1-3 and 94-98 age ranges. These cells were set

to the closest value that was not missing to prevent the plots from having large swings. Since the values in these cells were close to zero, this does not substantially affect the plots.

The 0-18 age range shown in Figure 16 shows that the Z-score trajectory appears to fit a linear pattern from ages 3 to 15. Ages 1 and 2 have little data and are unreliable. From ages 16 to 18 there appears to be a gradual deceleration in the rate of increase. It is not clear if the deceleration from 16 to 18 is due to the process occurring from ages 3-15 slowing down, or if this is due to the process that is occurring from 19 to 30 starting to have an effect.

A curvefit test was run in SPSS for the age range from 3-15. The linear model R² values were high (male R² = .976, female R² = .972), and the cubic model R² for males or females added less than .005 to the R² value. This does not appear to be strong evidence against a linear increase in the process creating the age crime curve from 3-15.

Figure 16: Z-scores for Male Age Crime Curve for 0-18 Year Olds (1996-2006)

The Z-score trajectory for the 19-45 year old age range is shown in Figure 17. The Z-score trajectory in this age range appears to fit a cubic model. There is a gradual deceleration curve from 19 to 30, and then a transition period from 30 to 45, followed by a steady decline from about age 45 onward. In subsequent analyses, this section will be split into two parts at age 35 in order to get a more precise picture of what is occurring.

Figure 17: Z-scores for Male Age Crime Curve for 19-45 Year Olds (1996-2006)

Figure 18: Z-scores for Male Age Crime Curve for 46-98 Year Olds (1996-2006)

The Z-score trajectory for the age 46 to 98 year old age range is shown in Figure 18. This section of the age crime curve appears to fit a linear model. The Z-scores appear to be declining at a steady rate each year. There might be a slight wave in the line, but any deviation from a linear model is minimal. A cubic model provided an R^2 value that was .001 higher than the linear model for both males and females when the curvefit procedure was used on Z-scores in the age range from 46-93. This does not seem a theoretically relevant improvement in accuracy.

In order to provide some idea of the relative magnitudes of the change in Z-score for males and females, the values of the model coefficients are shown below. While there do not appear to be major differences between the models, the reader should be cautioned the probabilities generated by Z-scores are very sensitive to small changes in magnitude.

Table 4: Z-Score Models for Selected Age Ranges

Ages	Model	a	b ₁	b ₂	R ²
Males					
3-15	Linear	-5.015	.224		.976
19-35	Quadrati c	.405	-.150	.002	.948
36-45	c	-4.855	.159	-.002	.731
46-93	Linear	-.391	-.043		.982
Females					
3-15	Linear	-5.223	.241		.972
19-35	Quadrati c	-.009	-.128	.002	.902

Fitting Hypothetical Strength and Brain Capacity Curve to the Z-score Model

It had been proposed that the strength and brain capacity levels over the life course were operating in opposing directions to create the Z-score trajectory for the age crime curve. As

strength increased, the Z-score for the age crime curve should increase, and as brain capacity increased, the Z-score for the age crime curve should decrease by an equal amount. In this section, this proposition will be tested to see if hypothetical strength and brain capacity curves could create the Z-score distribution for the age crime curve.

The mathematical form of the relationship between the Z-score and the strength and brain capacity levels should be as follows.

$$Z(\text{crime, age}) = a + b * (c * P(\text{strength, age}) - d * P(\text{brain, age}))$$

Where a,b,c, & d are constants

Some simple assumptions were made to create the following strength and brain capacity plots.

1. Strength and brain capacity are changing in a linear fashion in childhood and old age.
2. Strength peaks at age 25 and brain capacity peaks at age 30
3. There is a gradual transition between growth and decline
4. Declines in capacity are slower than the growth of capacity

Using these assumptions and a considerable amount of trial and error, the following two hypothetical curves for strength and brain capacity shown in Figure 19 were developed.

To develop the models shown, positive numbers were used to simplify the visualization process. Linear formulas were used to generate the ascending trajectories for strength and brain capacity. $\text{Capacity}_{(\text{age})} = \text{Capacity}_{(\text{age}-1)} + \text{Constant}$. It was assumed that there could be a slight acceleration in the decline with age, and so the decline curves were of the form $\text{Capacity}(\text{age}) = \text{Capacity}_{(\text{age}-1)} - \text{Constant} - \text{Constant} * (\text{age} - \text{zero age})$. Zero age was 25 for strength and 30 for brain capacity.

Figure 19: Hypothetical Strength and Brain Capacity Curves

At the transition between growth and decline, rounding factors were used to create a gradual transition. For instance, the constant growth factors at each successive year for the strength curve, starting at age 16 were multiplied by .9, .8, .7, etc. until the growth slowed to zero at age 25. Similarly, the decline was started gradually as well by multiplying the successive decline constant factors by .1, .2, .3, ..., 1.

Once the curves shown were generated, using simple addition, the level of brain capacity was subtracted from the level of strength at each year of age. The result was a score that was multiplied by a constant. Finally, 5.1 was subtracted from the total to provide the Z-score. The result was plotted along with the male Z-score trajectory to determine if the model could reproduce the age crime curve. The projected Z-score model generated from the hypothetical strength and brain capacity curves in Figure 19 is shown in Figure 20 along with the actual Z-score trajectory for males.

Figure 20: Projected Z-score Trajectory vs. Actual Age Crime Curve Z-scores for Males

There is not an exact match between the projected and actual Z-scores, but the model uses very simple assumptions. The strength and brain capacity trajectories are set up with similar formulas with only the constants being adjusted in the 0-15 and 46-98 age ranges. The transitions are smooth transitions with little custom manipulation.

The resulting projected age crime curve model is shown in Figure 21. To sum up the process that was used, the strength and brain capacity curves generated in Figure 19, are combined by subtracting brain capacity from strength levels, to generate the Z-score trajectory in Figure 20, which then is transformed using the NormSDist() function in Excel to generate the projected age crime curve in Figure 21. There is a correspondence between all three sets of trajectories.

Figure 20: Projected vs. Actual Male age Crime Curve

Conclusion

The purpose of this paper was to test Quetelet's biological explanation for the age crime curve. Quetelet proposed that changes in strength, passion, and reason over the life course were responsible for the age distribution of crime. Quetelet's model was simplified to an analysis of two trajectories, developmental changes in strength and brain development, because it appeared that changes in passion and reason were both caused by brain development. While the results of these analyses do not prove that changes in strength and brain capacity cause the age crime curve, the results demonstrate that biological development of strength and brain capacity could explain the age crime curve. If strength and brain capacity trajectories are combined, they appear to produce the Z-score trajectory for the age crime curve.

In developing the tests that were used, several logical inferences were made. The age crime curve is a population phenomenon and therefore it should be the result of changes in population parameters. The population parameters must be biological since the age crime curve

has a similar shape across cultures and social conditions. There must be a minimum of two biological processes, because the sharp inflection at age 18 could not be the result of changes in a single biological process. The most parsimonious theory should not use more than two biological factors to explain the age crime curve. Since it takes strength to commit a crime and mental capacity to avoid committing crimes, it was proposed that, as Quetelet proposed, strength and brain capacity are logical candidates for the processes that cause the age crime curve. Since crime should be directly related to crime levels, and brain capacity should be inversely related to crime levels, the age crime curve should be the result of some type of mathematical function that changes positively with changes in strength and negatively with changes in brain capacity. It was proposed that the level of strength, minus the level of brain capacity, should generate a Z-score trajectory that would create the age crime curve by adjusting the cumulative probability of criminal activity by age.

A preliminary examination of the age crime curve revealed that the age crime curve appeared to be composed of three separate sections. The sections ranged from ages 0-18, 19-35, and 36-98. Any model that was developed should fit these three sections.

An analysis of the life course trajectories of physical strength and mental capacity revealed the following. Physical strength increases from birth, peaks in the mid 20s, and declines in old age. Mental ability increases from birth, peaks in the mid 30s, and declines in old age. If it is assumed that rule breaking has a negative relationship with mental capacity, it is possible that the strength and brain development trajectories intersect to produce the age crime curves.

Given that both strength and brain capacity trajectories are changing in an approximately linear trajectory from 0-18 and from 46 to 98, it was postulated that there should be a linear

change in the Z-score trajectory underlying the age crime curve for these age ranges. Criminal propensity should increase with increases in strength and decline with increases in brain capacity. A Z-score model is a reasonable premise if the distribution of criminal propensity is distributed normally in the population.

A mathematical model was set up using linear formulas for ages 0-18 and 46-98 to generate Z-score trajectories for males and females and it was found that the models were able to reproduce the age crime curve with a high degree of accuracy. The explained variance against the average age crime curve trajectory was 99.9% for both the male and female models.

In a separate analysis, several other types of curves were generated in SPSS and compared with the projected cumulative probability distribution, that had been created with linear Z-score trajectories from 0-18, and 46-98. The projected age crime curve was superior to the SPSS generated curves and fit the data with the highest level of explained variance, explaining 92.4% to 98.3% of the variation in the sections.

In a further analysis, the age crime curve was transformed into a Z-score trajectory and the resulting Z-score trajectory was analyzed. A linear model was able to explain a high percentage of the variation in the Z-score sections from ages 3-15, and 46-98. The section from 19-35 appeared to fit a quadratic trajectory. The fit for any type of curve for the 36-45 year old data was not as good, suggesting that there was much more variation in this section.

In the final analysis, hypothetical curves for strength and brain capacity by age were generated. The predicted mathematical solution was that strength would positively add to the Z-score level for the age crime curve, and brain capacity would subtract from the Z-score level. It was demonstrated that the hypothetical strength and brain capacity curves could generate the age crime curve with a fair degree of accuracy.

The conclusions that can be derived from these findings appear to be as follows.

1. The age crime curve appears to be a cumulative probability distribution.
2. The Z-score trajectory for the age crime curve follows a linear trajectory from 0-18, a curvilinear trajectory from 19-45, and a linear trajectory from 46-98.
3. The results found are not incompatible with Quetelet's biological explanation for the age crime curve.

These conclusions will be discussed in depth in the sections that follow.

The age crime curve appears to be a cumulative probability distribution

One of the problems researchers have had with attempts to study the age crime curve was that there has been no consensus over the mathematical form of the age crime curve (Britt, 1992). The general consensus has been that there was a mixture of curves that all came together to create the age crime curve. The mixture approach was used by Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, and Visher (1986) in their research on criminal careers, Moffitt (1993) in her adolescent limited/life course persistent model, Laub and Sampson (2003) when looking at life course trajectories, and more recently by Sweeten, Piquero, and Steinberg (2013) when trying to fit a number of theoretically relevant variables to the age crime curve. Sweeten et al. (2013) concluded that it was highly unlikely that one or two variables operating alone could create the age crime curve.

The models developed here suggest that there appears to be support for the proposition that the age crime curve is a cumulative probability distribution of some type. It is possible that this curve could be driven by just two variables. This, in and of itself, would seem to be a significant finding.

The age crime curve is a three-part process

A cumulative probability distribution with age as a linear factor for the Z-scores fits the age crime almost perfectly from 0-18, and from 46-98. At least one other factor would be needed to fit the section of the age crime curve from 19-45. There would appear to be support for the hypothesis that the age crime curve has three sections.

Changes in strength and mental capacity could explain the age crime curve

While correlation does not prove causation, the data is consistent with Quetelet's proposition that strength and reason are important biological factors underlying the age crime curve. These data suggest that the age crime curve in the periods 0-18 and 46-98 is consistent with the hypothesis that the age crime curve is caused by changes in strength and brain capacity, since these biological factors change almost linearly in these age ranges.

It should be noted that many other biological factors also change linearly. For instance, height changes at a linear rate for most of the childhood years (Kuczmarski, Ogden, Guo, et al. 2000).. It should be noted that height does not decline linearly from 46-98, which would then require a separate explanation, which runs afoul of the parsimony rule.

If the reduction in the crime rate from 19-45 was due to increases in brain capacity, it would be expected that the decrease in arrest rates should flatten out in the mid thirties. This hypothesis also appeared to have some empirical support. Arrest rates drop from 19-30 and flatten out for a few years, reaching a minimum at about age 35, when mental capacity is at its peak. The arrest rates then begins to increase slightly before beginning to decline again at about age 40 when strength begins to decline.

Implications for future research

The analyses presented leave many questions unanswered. The model fit is very high, which suggests that the age crime distribution could be caused by changes in strength and age. However, it is not clear that the proposed trajectories are the actual trajectories of strength and crime. The model is very simple, but other factors could cause the age crime curve.

The actual strength trajectory should be measured to see when the changes in strength occur. This could be problematic however, since there are many ways to measure strength. Changes in speed by distance runners was presented as one method, but there are numerous other measures as well. Is there one type of strength that is more important than others?

Would there be inter-individual differences in the rate of crime by level of strength? This is an area that has had very little empirical study. This is rather odd since, as Adams (1997; p. 312) noted, the connection between strength and certain types of crimes is “obvious.”

Glueck and Glueck (1950; 1956), in one of the few studies that attempted to match physical strength characteristics with criminal activity, found that criminal offenders tended to have mesomorphic, or “muscular” body types. However, it is not clear that this applies to the current analyses, since muscular and strong could be different things. Sampson and Laub (1997) reanalyzed the mesomorphy data and suggested that mesomorphy did not predict future criminal behavior. In Quetelet’s explanation, strength is only a factor explaining the instantaneous level of crime, and not future crime.

The Mathematical Form of the Age Crime Curve

The cumulative distribution function of a normal curve is an integral function with the following formula.

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